

Pollen physiological dynamics of *Catharanthus roseus* after exposure to heavy metals

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Received: March 20, 2020 /Revised: April 2, 2020 /Accepted: June 25, 2020 /Published online: September 30, 2020
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Abstract

Pollen is the functional material for the gamete distribution among the plants. Pollen is affected by air pollutants which produce allergenicity and deformities on pollen surface. To reveals this we have evaluated the effect of Copper (Cu) and Zinc (Zn) metals on pollen physiological functions of *Catharanthus roseus*. The mean pollen germination % of control, Cu and Zn were significantly varied. We found that Cu and Zn both affects the pollen germination significantly ($p = 0.05$), however, pollen tube growth length were affected by the heavy metal exposure insignificantly ($p = 0.05$). To get more insight on this effect we were assigned data to two-way ANOVA which reveals us that the Cu, Zn and their interactions significantly ($p = 0.05$) affect both, pollen germination and pollen tube length. In correlation studied, we found significant ($p = 0.01$) correlation of metal and different metal concentrations with pollen germination % and pollen tube length. As the molecular weight and concentration of metal increases the pollen germination and tube length decreases significantly ($p = 0.01$) in the present study. Thus, from the above results, we concluded that heavy metal, as a pollutant, affects the pollen physiological functions, pollen germination and pollen tube length, significantly. Further study needed to find out what are the pollen modifications, morphological and chemical changes, occurring during metal exposure at higher concentrations.

Keywords: Pollen physiological function; pollen germination; heavy metal; toxicity; *Catharanthus roseus*

In recent years, anthropogenic activity produces the large amount of pollutants and these pollutants affects the environment by which living organisms like animals, plants and microbes are affected dramatically (Wolters and Martens 1987; Bruton et al. 2010). The plants were most common along the roadside of most of the cities. Among the plant part pollen are consider to be sensitive system (Wolters and Martens 1987). Air pollutant particles are adsorbed and accumulate on the surface of

pollen grains, therefore modifying pollen shape, structure and also induce allergen release and agglomeration of pollen material, including pollen proteins, on the surface of pollens (Mohsenzadeh, Chehregani, and Yousefi 2011; Ahmad et al. 2004). Releasing pollen allergens on the surface of pollen grains is one of the important reasons for allergy in polluted areas frequently. Different atmospheric pollutant such as SO₂ and NO₂ (Sousa et al. 2012), CO, O₃, SO₂ (Cuinica et al. 2015), particulate matters, acid rain (Ahmad et al. 2004; Ramaškevičienė et al. 2006), affects pollen allergy, germination and tube growth (Kalbande et al. 2008). Among these pollutants, metals are common pollutants (Showkat AM et al. 2007; Ünlü and Ersoz 2006; Ünlü and Ersoz 2007). These metal pollutants are accumulated

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on plants pollen and pollen serve as a bio indicator for environmental mentoring (Kalbande et al. 2008). Amongst the air pollutant heavy metals causes various effect on pollen germination (Munzuroglu and Nazmi 2000; Acharya, Sharma, and Chakraborti 2011; Wang et al. 2015) and adversely affect tube growth and ultrastructure (Sawidis and Reiss 1995). Inhibition of the pollen on the stigma by the simulated rain in the presence of copper is responsible for seed and fruit abortion (Cox 1988). From the last few years avenue plantation attracts the attention especially ornamental plants. *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G. Don is annual flowering herb and abundantly planted on the road divider, hence *C. roseus* preferred for present investigation to the study effects of heavy metal Copper (Cu) and Zinc (Zn) on pollen physiological dynamics i.e. pollen germination and tube growth length.

Pollen grains were collected soon after anther dehiscence from the flower of *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G. Don; grown at botanical garden Department of Botany, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati. Pollen grain culture medium was aqueous containing 40% sucrose (w/v) in deionised water without any supplement. Different concentrations of Cu (CuSO_4) and Zn (ZnSO_4) were made

Figure 1: Pollen germination % and Pollen Tube Length of *Catharanthus roseus* after in-vitro exposure to Zinc and Copper metal, A) Zn at 150 ppm, B) Zn at 200 ppm, C) Cu at 150 ppm, D) Cu at 200 ppm, E) Cu at 250 ppm (Scale 1 unit = 10 μm).

in demineralised water and mixed in aqueous culture medium to achieved said concentration of treatment group. Pollen was immersed in aqueous culture medium as treatment (with heavy metal) and control group (without heavy metal).

Pollen germination was achieved by sitting drop culture (Shivanna and Rangaswamy 1992). Pollen was incubated in germinating medium under 80-90% relative humidity in humid condition (Petri plate with moist filter paper) at $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hrs. Pollen germination was scored for at least 300 pollen grains for each metal concentration and control group. A pollen grain was considered to be germinated when the pollen tube length was twice the pollen diameter (Slomka et al. 2010). Percentage of pollen germination was determined under Trinacular fluorescence microscope (Carl Zeiss DSC-75) at central instrumentation cell (CIC), Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati.

After incubation as described above, pollen tubes were fixed by adding of 50% acetic acid to culture medium (Cox 1988). To estimate mean pollen tube length, at least 75 pollen tubes were measured in each concentration per replica. The effect of heavy metal on tube structure was observed under light microscope (Carl Zeiss make with digital camera Carl Zeiss DSC-75) at CIC, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati. The treatments on pollen germination and tube length consist of three replicates and data were represented by mean and standard deviations (mean \pm SD). All the data were assigned for one-way ANOVA, two-way ANOVA and Pearson Correlation in SPSS version 17.

Heavy metals affect plant development and reproduction if they are present in excessive amounts, a situation that is becoming increasingly common. Pollen is a convenient object for pollution assessment as it is in most cases a 2- or 3-cellular organism exposed to the environment. At the same time, pollen is a key stage in the life cycle of seed plants; pollen viability and efficiency of germination are crucial for reproductive success and crop yield (Karen, Searcy, and Mulcahy 1985; Breygina et al. 2017). In the present study, we have been evaluated *C. roseus* pollen to test effect of Copper (Cu) and Zinc (Zn) metal on pollen physiological dynamics at different concentrations in-vitro.

We have been recorded the mean germination % of control is 90.29 ± 1.06 and for Zn at 100 ppm is 77.39 ± 1.09 , at 150 ppm is

Table 1. Mean and Standard deviation of pollen germination and pollen tube length of *Catharanthus roseus* at different zinc and copper metal concentration (n=3)

Metal	Concentration	Germination %	Pollen Tube Length
Zinc (Zn)	Control	90.29±1.06	33.37±2.03
	100	77.39±1.09	67.52±1.60
	150	78.14±2.64	62.63±1.15
	200	69.38±1.12	50.50±1.25
	250	62.75±2.45	53.24±1.96
	Total	75.59±9.71	53.45±12.27
Copper (Cu)	Control	90.29±1.06	33.37±2.03
	100	57.48±2.49	38.27±1.05
	150	48.21±1.05	31.15±1.10
	200	22.26±1.13	21.17±1.10
	250	52.20±0.93	37.30±1.21
	Total	54.09±22.59	32.25±6.43
Total	Control	90.29±0.93	33.37±1.81
	100	67.44±11.04	52.89±16.07
	150	63.17±16.49	46.89±17.27
	200	45.82±25.83	35.84±16.10
	250	57.48±6.01	45.27±8.85
	Total	64.84±20.28	42.85±14.45

Values are mean± std. deviation (n=3).

Table 2: One-way ANOVA of pollen germination and pollen tube length of *Catharanthus roseus* at different metal concentration

Concentration	Germination %	Pollen Tube Length
Control	90.29±0.94 ^b	33.37±1.81 ^a
100	67.44±11.04 ^{ab}	52.89±16.07 ^a
150	63.17±16.49 ^a	46.89±16.10 ^a
200	45.82±25.49 ^a	35.84±8.85 ^a
250	57.48±6.01 ^a	45.27±14.45 ^a
Total	64.84±20.28	42.85±14.45

Values are mean± std. deviation (n=3); for each column, different lowercase letter significantly differ at $p \leq 0.05$ using Tukey's HSD.

Table 3: Two-way ANOVA to estimate effect of zinc, copper and their interaction on pollen germination and pollen tube length of *Catharanthus roseus*

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Zinc (Zn)	Germination %	3467.520	1	3467.520	1281.274	.000
	Pollen Tube Length	3370.376	1	3370.376	1496.522	.000
Copper (Cu)	Germination %	6440.825	4	1610.206	594.983	.000
	Pollen Tube Length	1572.183	4	393.046	174.521	.000
Zinc (Zn) X Copper (Cu)	Germination %	1968.195	4	492.049	181.816	.000
	Pollen Tube Length	1070.633	4	267.658	118.846	.000

Table 4: Pearson correlation between metals, concentrations, germination% and pollen tube length of the *Catharanthus roseus* pollen

	Metal	Concentration	Germination %	Pollen Tube Length
Metal	1	.000	-.539**	-.746**
Concentration		1	-.619**	.067
Germination %			1	.471**
Pollen Tube Length				1

**Correlation is significant at $p \leq 0.05$

78.14±2.64, at 200 ppm is 69.38±1.12, at 250 ppm is 62.75±2.45 and total average is 75.59±9.71 respectively (Table 1). The pollen tube length of control is 33.37±2.03 µm and for Zn at 100 ppm is 67.52±1.60, at 150 ppm is 62.63±1.15, at 200 ppm is 50.50±1.25, at 250 ppm is 53.24±1.96 and total average is 53.45±12.27 respectively (Table 1). We found that pollen germination % is reducing substantially with increasing Cu concentration while pollen tube length has unaffected. Pollen germination % significantly affected with Cu concentration, however, pollen tube length insignificantly (Table 2 and Fig. 1). Similar results have been reported by various authors for pollen germination, and they found substantial decrease at increasing the concentration of metals (Acharya, Sharma, and Chakraborti 2011).

For Copper metal, we found pollen germination 57.48±2.49 % at 100 ppm, 48.21±1.05 % at 150 ppm, 22.26±1.13 % at 200 ppm, 52.20±0.93 % at 250 ppm and total average is 54.09±22.59 % (Table 1). Pollen tube length for Cu is found to be 38.27±1.05 µm, 31.15±1.10 µm at 150 ppm, 21.17±1.10 µm at 200 ppm, 37.30±1.21 µm at 250 ppm respectively (Table 1 and Fig. 1). Heavy metals have become serious environmental contaminants in many countries following the period of rapid industrialization and urbanization (Mohsenzadeh, Chehregani, and Yousefi 2011; Karen, Searcy and Mulcahy 1985). Significant reduction in seed number was observed by the Karen et al. (1985) in *Silene dioica* (Caryophyllaceae) and *Mimulus guttatus* (Scrophulariaceae) after exposure to Cu and Zn metals. They concluded that these reductions in seed setting was due to the prezygotic loss of fertilization ability of the pollen (Karen, Searcy and Mulcahy 1985). In plant, *Reseda lutea* L. (Resedaceae), heavy metals can induce several abnormalities in pollen grains, ovule, and protein banding pattern, thus, they can affect the fertility, gene expression pattern, and survival of

plants (Mohsenzadeh, Chehregani, and Yousefi 2011).

We have subjected our data to one-way and two-way ANOVA to estimates effect of single and multiple variables to the physiological dynamics of the pollen (Table 2 and 3). We have recorded significant effect of metal concentration on both studies' parameter of the pollen. We also subjected to analyzed it with correlation and found significant relation between them. Different metal, different concentrations have significant correlation on pollen grain % and its ube length (Table 4). These results are in accordance with the earlier studies (Sawidis and Reiss 1995), that in germinating and growing pollen tubes heavy metals act primarily on cell wall development, and they concluded that in high pollution area, pollen tubes which are exposed to higher concentrations of heavy metals may influence higher plant reproduction (Sawidis and Reiss 1995; Sawidis 2008). Our study shows similar results with previous studies in different plant species. However, in *C. roseus* it our first report on such pollen physiological function dynamics in pollen study with elevated concentration of metals.

Acknowledgments:

Authors are thankful to Head, Department of Botany and authorities of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati, Maharashtra for providing necessary facilities.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

No Additional information is available for this paper.

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